

iQonic

IQONIC

Innovative strategies, sensing and process chains for increased Quality, re-configurability, and recyclability of Manufacturing Optoelectronics

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY / ABSTRACT

Currently, manufacturing processes, evolution of equipment and instrumentation are challenges generally affecting the opto-electronics and photonics industry, that is determined to follow higher customization and individualization. The European H2020 project “iQonic” aims for establishing a multi-sensorial component manufacturing and photonic system assembly hardware and software environment for zero-defect manufacturing. The following report is generated within the iQonic project and is focusing on the respective architecture to do so. Based on laser photonics use cases, such as quantum cascade lasers, high power diode laser stacks and others, a sensorial network aligned with the current industrial internet of things architectures utilizing edge devices, will acquire production defect relevant data at the interface of components manufacturing and system assembly hardware. This data represents descriptors for main sources of defects, in particular contamination and surface damages, as well as component irregularities, such as geometry deviations. The “near” real-time data, in conjunction with historian data, flows via a unified middleware layer from the sensorial network into a software based manufacturing model, based on artificial intelligence and a decision support system that allows for error compensation throughout the complete manufacturing chain, early malfunction detection on the component and system level, component-rework and re-assessment. Error compensation mainly takes place by selecting individual components and by pre-compensating for the effects of errors on the assembly hardware level. Consequently, aiming for zero-defect manufacturing during various stages of production, a key performance indicator (KPI) of the iQonic architecture is to lift the overall photonics assembly yield to 80%, decreasing the configuration time of the production environment and enabling for the use of recycled parts. Finally, the iQonic supply chain scalable and holistic architectural approach is under development, with the goal to provide flexibility, efficiency and sustainability to the manufacturing industry.

SCOPE

The report shall introduce a combined hardware and software structure overview that aims for zero-defect manufacturing of opto-electronical and photonic system. The main feature of the architecture shall be a multi-sensor network that acquires data throughout various processes of photonics manufacturing and assembly. Indications shall be given which type of data the sensor network shall collect throughout the manufacturing and assembly process chain. As this data will be a multitude of data of different types, a unification approach shall be discussed that offers this data to higher level intelligence such as decision support and knowledge-base systems. The main emphasis of higher level intelligence shall be the influence and adaption of the control of assembly processes for opto-electronic and photonic system, in order to improve quality and yield and in order to fulfill the general iQonic strategies:

1. **DIAGNOSE (DIA)** components and assembly hardware,
2. **ADJUST (ADJ)** the assembly hardware process parameters for new components and individual component’s properties,
3. **PREDICT (PRD) / DETECT (DET) / PREVENT (PRV) /SUSTAIN (SUS)** defects in components and assembled photonic systems,
4. **MANAGE (MAN)** alarms for the manufacturing and assembly hardware, and propose mitigation actions,
5. **REDESIGN (RED)** components and photonic systems for sustainability to ensure better disassembly, recycling, and requalification of the currently irreversible optical properties.

ABBREVIATIONS

ADJ	Adjust
DIA	Diagnose
PRD	Predict
PRV	Prevent
DET	Detect
SUS	Sustain
MAN	Manage
RED	Redesign
LED	Light emitting DIode
ZDM	Zero-Defect Manufacturing
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
RAMI 4.0	Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0
IoT	Internet of Things
IIoT	Industrial Internet Of Things
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications-Unified Architecture
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport
LAN	Local Area network
QoS	Quality-of-Service
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
CPS	Cyber-Physical System
DSS	Decision Support System
RSC	Reverse Supply Chain
PdM	Predictive Maintenance
EvMod	Event Modeler
SFCM	Shop Floor Communication Middleware
MLCM	Machine-Level Communication Middleware
HLCM	Higher-Level Communication Middleware
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
MES	Machine Execution System

1 Introduction

The manufacturing of optics evolved from the midst of 19th century to nowadays production, and basics like precision, stability, cleanliness and complex assembly procedures remain even increasing characteristic elements of the production process. The rapid growing availability of various types of light sources, such as various types of lasers and semiconductor based LED, lead to the term of photonics, that comprises both active and passive optical and electro-optical components, that are integrated to a complex illuminating or imaging system based on photons and light.

In the iQonic project, the partners will address the value chain for the production of active and passive opto-electronic and photonic system (Figure 1), in order to optimize it with respect to yield and quality, paving the way towards a zero-defect manufacturing of photonic systems. iQonic shall implement novel strategies for diagnosing and adjusting the properties of hardware and processes for photonics systems manufacturing, and shall investigate the prediction, detection, prevention and sustaining of defects in photonic component and systems by means of sensorics and their data analysis using modern data mining, big data and artificial intelligence approaches. Also, the management of alarms about defects and respective mitigation actions, and a re-design for sustainability to ensure better disassembly, recycling, and requalification may benefit from the gathering of data throughout the photonics value chain.

Thus, the iQonic architectural approach is a combination of the traditional hardware for the manufacturing of optical and photonics components and the assembly of systems out of those. The architecture shall comprise of an open, scalable and configurable sensor network throughout the manufacturing and assembly process chain, that gathers a broad variety of relevant data and that feeds this data in a unified format to software-based control processes. These allow for a feedback loop to the hardware processes, regarding the selection of components to be processed and regarding specific hardware parameters.

Figure 1: The optics and photonics assembly chain

The optics and photonics assembly chain, as depicted in Figure 1 in a generic way, poses demanding and increasing challenges, as it is composed of many process steps, from the manufacturing and preparation of components for the assembly process, via handling, alignment and finally bonding of component in the photonic system. During this complex and multi-step manufacturing, assembly and integration process chain, various sources of errors and defects result in yield ratios that are comparably low, in comparison to other industry sectors. Another challenge is that volumes in photonics production are often small to medium, with only a few applications reaching up to volumes higher than 10.000 p.a. The typically low volumes make it difficult to track down singular defects, their origins and their impact onto the final photonic system quality. In the same time, production systems have to be re-configurable in an easy way to adapt for new photonic product requirements and layouts. Nevertheless, knowledge about defects in the photonics manufacturing chain, and their impact onto the final photonic system quality is a mandatory pre-requisite for a modern, high yield and low to zero defect manufacturing. A combined approach of detecting defects by means of hardware technology and making use of the knowledge about the defect by a combined hardware and software architecture is subject of iQonic.

The architecture shall make use of a sensorial network within the photonics manufacturing process chain, aligned with state-of-the-art industrial internet of things architectures and utilizing edge devices, acquiring production defect relevant data. This data represents descriptors for main sources of defects, in particular contamination and surface damages, as well as component irregularities, such as geometry deviations. The “near” real-time data, in conjunction with historian data, flows via a unified middleware layer from the sensorial network into a software based manufacturing model, based on artificial intelligence and a decision

support system, that allows for error compensation throughout the complete manufacturing chain, early malfunction detection on the component and system level, component-rework and re-assessment. Consequently, aiming for zero-defect manufacturing during various stages of production, a key performance indicator (KPI) of iQonic is to lift the overall photonics assembly yield to 80%, decreasing the configuration time of the production environment and enabling for the use of recycled parts. Finally, the iQonic supply chain scalable and holistic approach is under development with the goal to provide flexibility, efficiency and sustainability to the manufacturing industry.

2 The combined hardware and software approach for the iQonic architecture

As already introduced, iQonic aims for a feedback loop for the hardware processes of components manufacturing (preparation) and system integration (handling of components, their alignment and bonding in a cycle for all required components to be integrated).

Figure 2 depicts the hardware process chain and architecture and its first interface layer to the software architecture. This interface layer is composed of the sensor data acquisition network. As discussed later, within the various hardware processes a multitude and variety of data can be created (images made by cameras and microscopes, pressure and force measurements, geometrical measurements etc.) by means of various and completely different types of sensors and sensor systems. A major requirement for the interface between hardware and software thus is a unification of the sensor data. To a certain amount, but not claiming to be complete, the sensor data types to be unified by means of the acquisition network are:

- Digital images, acquired by cameras with different types of imaging and magnification systems, e.g. microscopes, for the characterization of components,
- Vacuum sensors from hardware that is handling components by means of vacuum grippers,
- Force sensors from hardware that is handling components by means of mechanical grippers,
- Non contacting presence sensors such as capacitive sensors, light barriers etc. for detecting the presence of components,
- Distance sensors, mainly non-contacting (e.g. optical probes, cameras with microscope objectives, capacitive probes etc.) for geometrical measurements during alignment,
- Force sensor to measure contact during alignment,
- Various optical measurement technologies (beam profiling, interferometry, quadrant photodiodes etc.) for indirect probing of the aligned position by means of measuring the optical functionality of the component that is subject to assembly,
- Bonding agent solidification measurements (chemical probing),
- Sensors for global and localized environmental conditions of the manufacturing and assembly processes (temperature, humidity, vibrations etc.).

Figure 2: Generic interfaces between hardware and software

The second interface between hardware and software is process control. As the assembly is typically done either manually (then the interface is the human operator) or on (partially) automated platforms, as depicted in Figure 3, the interface is composed of the automation software and its data communication channel to the outer world. This data interface can simply be a typical data communication end-point through (REST WS) a local area network, depending on the implemented software architecture of the automation software.

Figure 3: Assembly platform and close-up to an assembly task within the platform (ficonTEC)

Independent from the chosen interface, the process control interface in general shall provide the following features to modify and adapt implemented manufacturing and assembly algorithms:

- Selection of specific components out of a batch of components for assembly, based on the component's individual characteristics,
- Compensate for individual characteristics of a component throughout the assembly processes, in particular during alignment (align at a “non-ideal” position, where a trade-off for the individual characteristics of the component still result in a tolerable performance), but also during handling (e.g. not making handling contact at surface areas with defects, in order not to accelerate defect growing) and bonding (e.g. take localized defects into account for dispensing the bonding agent, such as a glue),
- Compensate for known systematic errors of assembly processes, in particular for bonding effects (e.g. pre-compensation of bonding agent shrinkage, known from the ongoing characterization of assembled systems).

In the following section the out- and inputs to the different stages of the photonics manufacturing line, composing the main building blocks of the iQonic architecture, are discussed in more detail.

2.1 Hardware architecture

The hardware architecture focuses on the assembly process chain, as depicted in Figure 1. Thus, all pre-processes of component manufactured are assumed to be finished, including the (sometimes necessary) singulation of individual components out of a batch (e.g. a wafer). The components shall have been undergoing a respective cleaning procedure, incorporating a final inspection of the cleaning quality.

2.1.1 Preparation and feeding

The feeding and preparation process with respect to assembly then means that a certain version of defined component storage feeds the components in a deterministic way to the assembly environment. Typical versions of storage and feeding systems are e.g.:

- Blue tape (for wafer-scale manufactured, silicon or glass-based components that are already diced and cleaned afterwards on the blue tape),
- Gel-Packs and trays for individual components such as lenses, prisms etc.,
- Mechanical storage devices for passive components with more complicated geometries (e.g. fibers) or for components that require specific protection (see example in Figure 4),
- Electro-mechanical storage devices for active components that e.g. require electrostatic discharge protection.

According to Figure 4 there is a chance that the storage mechanism somehow influences the state of the component (e.g. when electrostatic discharge occurs for semiconductor devices, such as laser diodes), or the cleanliness (contamination) of the component (due to the fact that e.g. after cleaning the components have to be touched during insertion into the storage device). Thus, the iQonic architecture shall foresee to measure the state (functionality) and the cleanliness (contamination) of components that are fed to the assembly process chain. It would be the final characterization step of components, providing information for the control decision.

Figure 4: Preparation and feeding of components to the assembly process chain

The main control decision during feeding is the selection of an individual component for the actual assembly task. The selection of a component is based on a complex decision that takes into account for instance:

- The desired performance of the photonic system (requiring a model implementation of the optical performance and a feedback of the model output, using the actual component's state and performance parameters),
- Logistical boundary conditions (e.g. availability of components),
- Process knowledge about the behaviour of this type of component throughout the assembly process chain.

2.1.2 Handling

Aim of the handling process is to pick component out of the feeding and storage mechanism, to transport it to the assembly position, and to precisely hold the component during alignment and bonding. After bonding a release of the component shall be possible that does not influence the alignment state.

Most common handling technologies in optics and photonics assembly are vacuum grippers (Figure 5) and mechanical gripper (tweezers). As handling, using these technologies, is related to a contact between the handling tool (the gripper) and the component to be handled, specific precautions have to be taken and shall be subject to monitoring/ sensing during the handling process:

- The handling force shall be controlled in order to not damage sensitive components, also measuring the handling force can reveal mechanical contact of the component with system structures during alignment,
- The state and performance of the component might have to be measured, as handling forces can degrade the optical performance of the handled component (e.g. by deformation of optical surfaces, or by introducing birefringence into the component).

A major achievement of iQonic shall be not only the implementation of sensing techniques for the handling process, but also to investigate a handling tool with integrated sensing capabilities – the robotic hand by partner ShadowRobot.

Figure 5: Handling of components during the assembly process chain

The control for the handling process shall mainly adapt the handling force. As the handling force shall compensate for counter forces (weight, accelerations and momentums, bonding forces) while introducing lowest possible influence, always a trade-off has to be found that represents an optimum, that is relevant for the individual component handled during the actual assembly task.

2.1.3 Alignment

Alignment is the most crucial process step in optical, opto-electronics and photonics assembly, as the alignment state of a component defines its performance within the overall performance of the photonic system. Alignment often needs to be done in the micron and even sub-micron range, and in up to six degrees of freedom.

Two main principles of alignment can be nominated:

1. Passive alignment, performed by placing the optical component against a mechanical stop provided by the structure of the system (a most common example is to place fibers into a v-groove),
 - As the position of the component is defined by the contact between component and the mechanical stop, sensing the contact is representative for a measurement of the alignment state.
2. Active alignment, measuring the position of the component within the system, either directly (geometrical measurement) or in-directly (by measuring the optical performance) and providing a feedback loop to the positioning system to minimize the position error,
 - The direct position of a component can be measured by means of representative alignment marks, or by observing geometrical features (optical surfaces, non-optical surfaces or structures) by means of camera observation or by observation using dedicated instruments (e.g. autocollimators, interferometers),
 - The optical performance as indirect representation of the component's position is nevertheless the most accurate indication of the desired position. Performance is measured in various ways (intensity, homogeneity, wave-front, spectral properties etc.) and strongly depends on the actual application of the photonic system.

Figure 6: Alignment of an optical component during the assembly process chain

Control of the alignment (Figure 6) has to consider the following parameters that shall be provided by the feedback from the iQonic software architecture:

- Alignment not to the ideal position, but to the position the model trade-off between the actual component's characteristics and performance reveals,
- Pre-compensation of effects of the sub-sequent bonding process, as these are typically irreversible and thus cannot be corrected for afterwards,
- Pre-compensation of environmental effects, such as temperature or vibrations.

It has to be taken into account that the alignment of optical components with respect to their functionality can be a time consuming, iterative and non-deterministic procedure. Typical problems that occur are local optima that are not the global optima, non-deterministic procedures and cross-influences of degrees of freedom for alignment.

2.1.4 Bonding

Bonding is the final process step in the assembly process chain, and it as important as alignment itself. Bonding fixates the achieved alignment state with respect to the life time of the product, and vs. the environmental conditions for transportation and usage. Bonding technologies in optics, opto-electronics and photonics are clamping, or using a media (glue, solder) as a bonding agent. Using a bonding agent is the most common technology, as this allows for bonding different materials together in a heterogeneous system integration, and as it allows integrating functionality into the bonding area, e.g. for electrical and thermal conductivity. Using bonding agents allow to have complex assembly situations and configurations, as the dispensing of the bonding agent can easily be done in even complex assembly environments. The fast curing of UV-polymerizing acrylates by means of UV illumination in the 10..30 s time regime enables a fast fixation of the alignment state. In order to determine the quality of the bonding process using bonding agents, the following precautions for process characterization and sensing have to be taken into account:

- Localized environmental conditions, in particular temperature and humidity, can influence the wetting and solidification performance of the bonding agent,
- The precision of the dispensed volume, the precision of its application at the bonding area, and the performance of the application of the curing mechanism (e.g. intensity, wavelength and duration of an UV illumination) influence the alignment result, in particular due to the shrinkage of the bonding agent during resolidification (in the range of 1..10%),

- Resolidification might result in outgassing of bonding agent ingredients, in particular volatile organic compounds (VOC). Those might be absorbed then on optical surfaces, causing their degradation. VOC shall be measured by means of chemical sensing; the SACMI electronic “nose” is foreseen for this task.

Laser-soldered Fiber in V-Groove

Figure 7: Bonding of a component during the assembly process chain

The control of the bonding process (Figure 7) shall focus on the control for applying the bonding agent and its resolidification mechanism:

- Dispensing the bonding agent by means of controlling pressure and time of a droplet generation mechanism (precision down to the nanolitres scale) or any other dispensing mechanism,
- Controlling the positioning of the dispensing tool, e.g. by camera observation, or by calibration,
- Controlling the curing device, e.g. by monitoring the intensity and wavelength shift of an UV lamp.

2.1.5 Summary

The following summarizes the findings of the hardware process analysis for the iQonic architecture. It becomes obvious that the iQonic architecture shall sense a number of common parameters (environment, forces), that it shall provide dedicated image acquisition and analysis capability, and that it shall have an open architecture to implement a variety of different measurement principles regarding optical alignment. iQonic specifics will be the measurement of forces during handling and the detection of VOC, resulting from bonding.

The main controls in the iQonic architecture are the selection of components based on modelling, taking individual properties of components into account, the position of the component during alignment, taking various pre-compensation opportunities and requirements into account, and individual process parameters (handling forces, curing parameters etc.).

Table 1 also indicates, where there is a chance to apply one of the eight iQonic strategies (diagnose, adjust, predict, detect, prevent, sustain, manage, and redesign) in detail.

Table 1: Sensor requirements and controls for the assembly chain processes in the iQonic architecture

No.	Sensorics	Control	DIA	ADJ	PRD	DET	PRV	SUS	MAN	RED
Preparation and feeding										
1	Component's state and performance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Damage (scratches, digs etc.) • Material and composition • Geometry • Surface properties and coatings • Functionality 	Selection of components <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performance prediction • Yield optimization 	X		X	X		X	X	X
2	Contamination <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Particles • Organic contaminations • Anorganic contaminations 		X		X	X	X		X	
Handling										
3	Handling force	Handling force	X	X		X	X		X	
4	Component presence		X			X			X	
5	Component's state and performance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functionality 		X		X	X		X	X	X
Alignment										
6	Mechanical contact at stops	Position	X		X	X	X		X	
7	Geometric position <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment marks • Geometry features on optical and non-optical surfaces and component structures (edges, corners) 		X	X		X		X	X	X
8	Optical functionality and performance		X		X	X		X	X	X
9	Environmental conditions	Environmental parameters	X	X		X		X	X	
Bonding										
10	Environmental conditions	Environmental parameters	X	X		X		X	X	
11	Dispensing parameters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volume • Area 	Dispensing parameters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volume • Area 	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
12	Curing parameters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UV intensity, wavelength, duration • temperature 	Curing parameters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UV intensity, wavelength, duration • temperature 	X	X		X		X	X	X
13	Contamination <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volatile organic compounds 		X		X	X	X		X	X

2.2 Software Architecture

According to Figure 2 there are two main interfaces for the software architecture. While the control interface to the assembly hardware (also called: shopfloor) is a "simple" data interface, where the majority of intelligence shall be implemented in the software that influences the assembly algorithms, the sensor network interface is far more complex.

2.2.1 Multi-Sensor Hardware Layout

The multi-sensorial data acquisition network is realized at Work Station Level (WSL) on the Shop Floor (layer 1-3, according to RAMI 4.0 [1]). The architecture design is aligned with the RAMI 4.0 reference architecture incorporating technologies towards industry 4.0 paradigm.

As seen in Figure 8, it consists of different types of devices (i.e. SACMI electronic "nose", FiconTec, FORTH) and sensors (i.e., temperature/ humidity, accelerometers, positions, presence, force, images), producing a heterogeneous set of data related to the production process and assembly components. This heterogenous data set, in terms of type, kind, size and sampling rate is harmonized against acquisition time index instance and shaped following a predefined data model. More specific, the ITK Daedalus edge IoT (SFCM [2]) acquires all the relevant data from the sensors and shop-floor devices (data sources), aggregate (processing, harmonized) and transmits them through a message bus mechanism, using MQTT communication protocol to the higher-level (HLCM) components of the iQonic platform. The ITK Daedalus low level interface communicates with the data sources through well-established protocols such as Modbus, TCP/IP, REST Web Services, but also through latest communication protocols, such as OPC-UA and MQTT.

Figure 8: Multi-sensorial data acquisition network

The flexibility of the ITK Daedalus edge device through its modular design, local KPI calculations and its HMI for visualization and alerts unifies the heterogeneity of the shop floor, it is digitized and transformed it to a "smart" shop floor as industry 4.0 dictates. This allows the iQonic platform to provide suggestions and actions through the high-level components DSS, CPS, PdM, EvMod and RSC to the operator at the shop floor at the current phase of the production.

2.2.2 Sensor Network Middleware

Middleware is a software layer that sits between applications and objects. The aid of an efficient middleware platform is required to tackle all these wide collection of issues regarding functionality, technology, heterogeneity of devices and services [3]. Middleware aims to provide solutions to frequently encountered problems, such as heterogeneity, interoperability, security and dependability [4]. The most challenging problem is the heterogeneity of different objects. The specific problem can be addressed by deployment of a suitable middleware, which sits between things and applications, operating as a reliable platform for communication among components with different interfaces, operating systems and architectures. Middleware can be considered as a "network-oriented" vision [5].

There is a significant growth in middleware development daily due to the fact that this enabler facilitates the easier combination of new services and previous technologies, to produce a novel and more capable service.

Interoperability is a desired functionality that makes it possible for two sets of applications on interconnected networks to be able to exchange data and services meaningfully with different assumption on protocols, data models, and configuration, without any problems and additional programming efforts by the developers [6]. It is the nature of software and hardware heterogeneity of IoT that requires interoperable components. An IoT Middleware is supposed to work with numerous diverse and heterogeneous devices, technologies and applications, which is a very challenging task [7]. Thus, interoperability is a vital necessity for the iQonic Middleware and it has different degrees depending on the heterogeneity level of the environment or system components. All the heterogeneous components, having different data and communication standards, should be able to interact without any time delay. Therefore, the middleware should provide syntactic as well as semantic interoperability [8].

Flexibility is an important feature that middleware should offer. There are different kinds of flexibility (e.g. response time or delay flexibility). It is essential to determine which software or hardware components require more flexibility. The level of flexibility is important because higher level of flexibility requires more connectivity APIs [6]. Additionally, middleware should expose transparency by hiding architectural information details and complexities from both application and object sides, allowing them to communicate with minimum knowledge of each other side's information. This distinctive characteristic is beneficial for programmers, end users and applications. Furthermore, portability is a critical feature in IoT, since many mobile hardware and software components are constantly moving between different platforms. Therefore, an IoT platform communicates from everywhere, anytime, with any device, helping to boost portability by its flexibility. It helps move across the environment and avoids being restricted to one platform. Middleware runs in user side and can provide independence from network protocol, programming language, OS and others.

A vital issue in middleware is security due to the fact that most data transmission and operation occur through it. A secure system requires confidentiality, integrity and availability considerations. Therefore, middleware should provide different security measures for ubiquitous applications and pervasive environments. Authentication of identification and credentials, authorized modifications and access control policy are required [9]. Regarding privacy, all IoT system components that access personal user information must guarantee protection of the mentioned information from unauthorized access. Maintainability is the ability of the systems, applications or devices to respond to failures properly and rapidly return to normal functionality without any problem. This is achievable by isolating, correcting, repairing, preventing and other acts of resolving defects. Maintainability has a fault tolerance approximation. The growth of deploying IoT in different contexts is significant. Without proper maintainability in middleware, extending the network or fixing the bugs would be overwhelming. Therefore, it is important to design a maintainable software from the outset. Provision of relevant documentations and feedback checklists can be helpful in designing stable and extendable middleware [6].

The iQonic hardware and sensor acquisition network includes multiple heterogeneous devices and diverse resources. Therefore, the appropriate knowledge of these resources is required to be available for achieving the appropriate and timely working of the system, since the iQonic environment is highly dynamic. Resource discovery is the term for this gathering of information and it is a necessity. One of the key essentials of Resource Discovery mechanism for middleware is to cope with frequent failures. Self-stabilizing algorithms should be used to bring the system into an ordinary state despite transient failures. It should be automatic and adaptive as human intervention is not feasible for such a large IoT network [10]. Since IoT is a system with constrained resources and those resources being shared by multiple applications and services, it becomes extremely important to manage the resources to achieve the desired Quality-of-Service (QoS). There should be services for the monitoring, allocation and provisioning of resources. The services should be capable to resolve resource conflicts that might arise because of the sharing of resources and multiple concurrent applications. The middleware should be capable enough to accommodate the resource management with a distributed, scalable and dynamic approach [11].

2.2.3 Zero-Defect Manufacturing Software Architecture

Figure 9 shows the approach for a zero-defect manufacturing software architecture (ZDM). The aim of this holistic and effective ZDM software architecture is to bring Industry 4.0 into a state-of-the-art manufacturing line for opto-electronical and photonic systems, achieving the flexibility and sustainability of their production. The scalable and easily deployable architecture shall cover various ranges of the overall process chain, in particular, also including (next to the assembly process chain itself) the design of new opto-electrical components, and their disassembly and reintroduction into the value chain at their end-of-life time.

Following this strategy, industries can enhance product quality, reduce waste, increase productivity by automated, intelligent and self-adaptive process control, increasing both low and high-volume productions yields, raising faster reconfiguration times, while providing more designs and reintroduction of recycled components to reduce the material costs. The main objectives of the ZDM approach are to get zero defects in a photonic production environment, to achieve waste/scrap reduction, lower production costs, shorter production times, higher productivity and competitiveness. The ZDM approach aims at a higher resource and energy efficiency. Among the challenges that the ZDM approach brings to industries are the following: The identification of error sources and types, the identification of most problematic phases within a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach, the clustering of errors and subsequent solutions according to the most common levels in an industrial shop-floor activity, and finally, the development and implementation of suitable ZDM tools, as solutions for the upstream generation and downstream propagation of production defects [12].

Figure 9: ZDM software architecture overview

Figure 9 illustrates an overview of the ZDM software architecture, where the data gathering starts at the pilot shop floor using various sensors (environmental data, contamination, optical performance, images) and positioning systems. Data collection occurs throughout the manufacturing process, along with the inspection of the production line. A series of sensors and actuators at the shop-floor assembly process chain level take readings for both the intrinsic and extrinsic machine's key performance parameters. The intrinsic parameters represent each factor that affects the assembly hardware's behaviour on system level, such as structural health, degradation of components, energy consumption, production rate, temperature, etc. The extrinsic parameters involve factors that do affect the machine's performance, but are not in the system level, such as ambient conditions, temperature, humidity, operator's or system's inputs, etc. For each of the deployed use-cases there should be a different set of intrinsic and extrinsic parameters.

Furthermore, visual sensors (cameras) will be used for image acquisition and for monitoring product quality, according to the requirements for each use case. The goal of this approach will be to categorize the components for assembly into quality classes. All of the components qualification results will be stored according to the quality inspection based on the requested quality, expected quality and actual quality. All collected data are logged into servers with time indexes, transferred through a local area network (LAN) to the shop floor communication middleware (SFCM), where a Daedalus software enables full exploitation of the cyber-physical system (CPS) virtualized intelligence concept. Daedalus fully accepts the concept of vertically integrated automation pyramid. In Daedalus it has been acknowledged deeply that CPS intrinsic existence defies the concept of rigid hierarchical levels, being each CPS capable of complex functions across all layers. New levels of vertical and horizontal integration can be envisioned thanks to the peculiar service-oriented approach proposed by Daedalus. In fact, current Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) can extend their scopes of application towards the shop floor by being capable of directly accessing the information flows and elaboration functionalities of the automation CPS. Moreover,

non-real-time and bidirectional exchange of information can exist between devices, even if they are not explicitly orchestrated, such as among products and manufacturing equipment, or between systems of different departments across the production value chain [13].

As far as the machine-level communication middleware (MLCM) is concerned, the publish/subscribe communication is adequate for the required information dissemination model of sensor network applications. An information supplier publishes messages that are forwarded to one or more subscribers (one-to-many communication). An extension to this basic model allows messages being associated to topics. The subscribers only receive messages associated with the exact topic(s) to which they have subscribed. The key elements in the publish/subscribe communication are the notification service and the buffer, where the messages are queued before they are passed to subscribers. The notification service takes responsibility to inform the subscribers when a new message arrives. In this way, it allows the asynchronous communication as producers and consumers are fully decoupled. This loose coupling is the prime advantage of this kind of communication in the context of ad-hoc and pervasive environments, such as sensorial networks [14].

PdM processes data obtained by the machines for adjustment of production processes, using the machine learning system to predict quality of products. Furthermore, the holistic monitoring system – Event Modeler - (EvMod) exploits the real time machine data of the condition and performance throughout the production, allowing the sustainability in the manufacturing process. Following, CPS is hierarchically orchestrated in real time within the shop-floor, to achieve complex and optimized behaviours. CPS will provide the processed data i.e. defected part, production stage etc., to the reverse supply chain (RSC). Along with data from CPS, RSC also receives the processed data through the higher-level communication middleware (HLCM) and computes it ensuring the reusability and requalification of the products. HLCM as an extra layer is applied to the communication with other higher-level management systems i.e., decision support system (DSS) and RSC. HLCM uses publish/subscribe communication pattern and communicates the company's MES/ERP to the DSS, which analyses the defects along with the PdM predictions, categorizing them based on their severity, while ensuring the production line to have high performance, accuracy and fidelity. The defects are processed by the DSS and are interfaced with MES. To meet the requirements of zero-defect manufacturing, a holistic framework and a comprehensive set of integrated strategies should be provided. They should encompass the whole manufacturing line. The proper strategies and associated technologies should effectively minimize product defects in a multi-stage production line in manufacturing systems. Each of the following strategies, as the name suggests, serves a different role which act synergistically with the others: Diagnose, Predict, Adjust, Prevent, Detect, Manage, Sustain and Redesign.

Decision making in the event of a defect will take place. The defect will be analysed via the DSS, from which the defect can be classified and categorized on its severity. In case of “repairable” defects, the system will decide the following: (i) rework on the spot, (ii) removal from the production line for further inspection and rework. If the defect is classified as “non-repairable” then the system will decide whether (a) the product will be forwarded to upstream stages, or (b) considered as total failure where it will be recycled. To facilitate the implementation of the eight strategies, a policy to support a “reverse supply-chain” has been considered, in the context of a multi-stage supply-chain attached to a multi-stage production. As a result, the defected products/parts detected in downstream stages (produced during a stage, or provided from suppliers in a particular stage) could be returned to upstream stages (internal or external supply-chain tiers) for remanufacturing or recycling.

2.2.4 Towards Zero-defect Manufacturing using Artificial Intelligence

To realise the aim of the iQonic solution, the key enabling technology is Artificial Intelligence (AI). Exploiting the historic data generated by the sensing systems, different AI solutions will be deployed to Detect, Diagnose and Predict. The first AI technology will be integrated in the stages of visual inspection; a Deep Learning (DL) instance aware semantic segmentation system to enable detection, classification and severity evaluation of defects. The goal of the system will be to characterize the image at a pixel level and provide extracted analytics for either on the spot decisions (Go/No-go) or knowledge to be evaluated at a later system (progression of defect appearance or severity). This is an area where a lot of effort has been performed for Autonomous Vehicles research and many contributions are found in the literature using as basis Convolutional Neural Network layers (CNNs) [15, 16, 17]. iQonic's approach will make use of those state of the art architectures and modify them for the application scenarios utilizing transfer learning techniques as well as pretraining.

In the era of Industry 4.0, machine health could not be omitted from the holistic picture. Therefore, the second AI technology that will be integrated in iQonic, will be a machine health evaluation system. The process of implementing the solution will start with Anomaly Detection networks, especially those able to capture the

multivariate problem dimensionality, like Deep Auto-encoders based on Dense, CNN or Long Short Term Memory cells [18, 19, 20]. For the system to detect abnormal operating conditions, means training takes place in known “normal” operating condition data as designated by expert opinion. This approach is particularly effective when there are no labelled conditions in historical data and can be used as an intermediate state to achieve either classification of machine state, once expert knowledge is fused in the dataset, or prediction of the appearance of defective products due to machine’s deteriorating state. Combining both technologies, will be crucial towards realization of a zero-defect production, where defects occurring to external factors will be stopped before they are propagated downstream and machine conditions that deviate from “normal” and lead to defective products will be remedied by a Decision Support System operating on the aforementioned AI technologies.

2.3 Functional overview for the envisaged, specific hardware and software components

2.3.1 Process chain optimised designs for micro-macro assembly and disassembly (Fraunhofer)

2.3.1.1 Component description

The traditional process chain for the assembly of photonic systems takes ideal component properties and an ideal assembly result (mainly characterised by the alignment status, but also by electro-optical characteristics of the photonic components and the overall photonic system) into account. Only specific and typically high volume applications also consider more intelligent approaches that make use of assembly statistics, component properties and environmental conditions. Nevertheless, the potential of such process data is also relevant for low and mid-volume photonics production, even for the integration of singular, individual systems.

The optimized process chain for the assembly of photonic systems paves the way for making use of component characteristics, assembly environment data and actual assembly results upon the achieved alignment result before bonding. It allows for the selection of components for an individual photonic product, independent from the production volume. Environmental data as well as assembly process data then is used to constantly update the alignment status that shall be achieved – this status might differ from the ideal alignment status, taking assembly statistics (process and environment related) and individual component characteristics into account. The calculation of the updated assembly goal and status shall be made by a higher level intelligence, that updates in real time parameters of the alignment process.

A specific feature of the optimized process chain design is the usage of organic or anorganic-based bonding agents for the fixation of components. Characteristics of the bonding agent, as well as of the bonding parameters, shall be fed to a higher level intelligence and data basis, that will store information about the disassembly potential for the assembled system and components integrated in it.

2.3.1.2 Main inputs

- Initial characteristics of active and passive optical components to be used for the integration of a photonic systems
 - Geometrical parameters
 - Electro-optical parameters
- Selection of components, based on components characteristics
- Environmental data for the integration platform
 - Global and localized temperature, humidity, vibrations, VOC
- Process data for individual assembly and integration steps
 - Handling forces
 - Status and results of initial alignment
- Characteristics of bonding agents for disassembly purposes
- Characteristics of active and passive optical components used for the integration of the photonic systems, after alignment
 - Geometrical parameters
 - Electro-optical parameters

2.3.1.3 Main outputs

- Bonding process characteristics for disassembly purposes
- Characteristics of active and passive optical components used for the integration of the photonic systems, after bonding (and eventual post-baking)

- Geometrical parameters
- Electro-optical parameters
- Characteristics of the integrated and assembled photonic systems, after bonding (and eventual post-baking)
 - Geometrical parameters
 - Electro-optical parameters

2.3.1.4 Functionality summary

The optimised process chain for the assembly and disassembly of photonic systems makes use of the standardized process chain, but is taking component data, environmental characteristics and assembly data upon the initial alignment status into account to decide about an alternative alignment status, based on the findings of a higher level intelligence. Also the results of the bonding process (in particular the deviated alignment status after bonding) is fed to the higher level intelligence for an update in follow-up assembly procedures. Specifics of the bonding process are also made public to the disassembly potential stored in the higher level intelligence and product data.

2.3.1.5 Component diagram

Figure 10: Optimized assembly chain

2.3.2 Adaptive Laser Raster-Scanning Optical Workstation (FORTH)

2.3.2.1 Component description

The optical apparatus is based on a modified fully-motorized microscope with excitation source a fs-laser (1030nm, 90fs, 76MHz). The laser beam is passing through a pair of galvanometric mirrors (GM), which are moving accordingly to create a raster-scanning scheme, it enters the microscope and it is tightly focused onto the sample using a high numerical-aperture objective (40x/1.3NA). While the beam is moving and it is raster-scanning the sample, the detectors (which are based on photomultiplier tubes (PMT)) are recording the signal at frequent time intervals from every point of the sample. By correlating the recorded signals with the position of the GM, an image is created. In our system, following the above procedure we acquire an image of 500x500 measurements (pixels) in ~1s and one of 900x900 pixels in ~3s. The optical resolution provided by the system is in the sub-micron scale (~700nm radial and ~1100nm axial resolutions). Depending on the scanning speed, the pixel size is defined. The wide-field channel of the CCD-detector is equipped with digitally adaptive z-correction module.

Figure 11: Adaptive Laser Raster-Scanning Optical Workstation, performance in thin films inspection

2.3.2.2 Main optical parameters inputs

The main optical parameters that can be adjusted during imaging are:

- Laser wavelength
- Laser power
- Excitation polarization
- Magnification
- Pixel size
- Number of points
- Voltage to size relation of scanning area
- Band pass detection selection
- Detector voltage amplification

2.3.2.3 Main optical parameters outputs

- Adaptive corrected imaging
- Digitally adapted z-correction
- Laser raster-scanning imaging microscopy
- Direction of detected polarization
- Pixel-by-pixel orientation of scatterers (for non-linear)
- Pixel-by-pixel anisotropy parameter (for non-linear)

2.3.2.4 Functionality summary

The adaptive in-line laser raster-scanning optical system could provide real-time feedback in the process flow and in the in-chain inspection of the materials assembly and manufacturing parameters. To evaluate with high precision the material parameters (e.g. structure, thickness, position) during the process, diffraction limited resolution is required. Experimentally, the diffraction limited resolution is compromised due to aberrations. In order to solve this problem we use digital adaptive corrections in the wide field optical imaging and state-of-the-art laser raster-scanning imaging microscopy. The desired imaging characteristics (pixel size, resolution, magnification etc) can be adjusted by changing the optical parameters inputs.

2.3.2.5 Component diagram

Figure 12: Component diagram of the Adaptive Laser Raster-Scanning Optical Workstation

2.3.3 Active and passive component bonding processes in micro-optics (TAU)

2.3.3.1 Component Description

The bonding processes employed in the IQONIC framework must fulfil many different requirements (including positioning tolerances, mechanical strength, thermal, aging, and reliability requirements) in the broad field of micro-optic applications. Due to the broad range of applications, the requirements set to the bonding processes can significantly vary between different assembly types. Therefore, the bonding processes in IQONIC framework must include flexibility to adapt many different requirements and micro-optics components. On the other hand, high flexibility usually increases the complexity in automated processes, which are needed to meet the production cost, quality, and throughput requirements in micro-optic assembly processes. To combine flexibility with the automated assembly process, IQONIC bonding processes enable fast (automatic) assembly system reconfiguration and the adaptation of assembly setups by modularization.

The main functionality of this technology component in IQONIC solution is to define generic frameworks for the bonding process chains of active and passive components and provide common modular bonding procedures for different component types, that can be adjusted based on the special requirements of different type micro-optical assemblies. The target of the active and passive component bonding process design is to enable flexibility, excellent performance, and high reliability with low production costs. The functionalities of this activity also include characterization of bonding performance, quality, and reliability. The characterization can be used as a feedback to adjust the process parameters to optimize the key performance indicators of the process chain and assemblies.

2.3.3.2 The main inputs of the technology component

The list of inputs for this IQONIC technology component is

- requirements and restrictions given by the end users
- components, substrates, subassemblies and their specifications
- handling tools and their specifications
- assembly and characterization systems and their configuration
- optical, thermal, mechanical and electrical design

- the KPIs of the micro-optic assembly
- environmental parameters
- instructions to adjust the bonding parameters.

2.3.3.3 The main outputs of the technology component

The outputs of the IQONIC technology component

- the design of modular bonding procedures for active and passive micro-optic components
- assembled components and substrates
- recyclable components and substrates
- wasted components (damaged or other non-recyclable components and substrates)
- KPIs for both assembly and bonding process
- bonding process parameters
- characterization data from the bonding and performance and reliability

2.3.3.4 Functionality summary from the technology component

The technology component has three main sub-components which are described below.

- Design stage: the bonding process chain design is defined based on the inputs provided by the end user, assembly system, components, and the KPIs of the assembly. The design is following the modular IQONIC bonding process chain model. The design stage also defines the KPIs for the bonding process itself, the initial process parameters at certain environmental conditions, and the initial assembly system configuration.
- Preparation stage: the components are prepared, bonding process parameters are loaded, and the assembly system is reconfigured if needed. Component data is also loaded. The parameters are adjusted based on the possible feedback given by DSS and the data generated by previously assembled components.
- Assembly stage: the process chain model, components, assembly system configuration, process parameters, and KPIs are used as inputs to carry out the component assembly and bonding processes.
- Post-assembly stage: the KPIs of the assembly and the bonding process are measured and stored, bonding process parameters are stored, components and (sub)-assemblies are positioned, so that these are ready for the following assembly stage.

2.3.4 UR10 + Shadow Robot Dexterous Hand (SHADOW)

2.3.4.1 Component Description

The UR10 is an out-of-the-box collaborative industrial robot arm with 6 DOF and 10kg payload. The Shadow Robot Dexterous Hand is an anthropomorphic robotic gripper with 20 actuated DOF, absolute position and force sensors and touch sensors on the fingertip. Both arm and hand are separately connected to a control computer via 2 ethernet cables. The hand is provided with a 48V power supply. The hand is connected to the robot arm via an elbow adaptor plate.

Figure 13: UR10 + ShadowRobot hand system

The software to control the UR10+Hand system is developed in ROS. The custom-developed driver interfaces the robot with ROS.

2.3.4.2 Data inputs

Possible control commands available:

- Trajectory commands
 - Joint_names
 - Joint Trajectory Points
 - Array of joint positions
 - time_to_execute_points
- Position commands
- PWM commands

2.3.4.3 Data outputs

- Joint position
- Tactile sensor data
- Pressure measurement
- IMU data

2.3.4.4 Functionality summary

The UR10 + Hand system can be controlled to perform manipulation and grasping actions. Position control is currently implemented by using ROS's standard PID position controller. For the hand, the output of the host side PID controller is sent to the motor as a PWM demand, while for the arm the output is sent to as position demands. Trajectories commands can be sent to the robot to execute complex motions. The various trajectories are translated into position commands to execute following time profiles, and then sent to the robot. The state of the robot is constantly fed back to the control computer to evaluate the current robot position. The hand data is made available to the user from 100Hz and up to 1kHz via a high bandwidth EtherCAT interface. Sensor data and command interface can be used by higher level controllers, path planners and state machines to execute given complex tasks. Sensors might be added or replaced in the course of the project to achieve certain use cases, if deemed necessary.

2.3.4.5 Component diagram

Figure 14: UR10 + Hand system diagram

2.3.5 Olfactory system for detecting contamination – SACMI EOS507E (SACMI)

2.3.5.1 Component Description

EOS507E is an instrumental odour monitoring system (IOMS, or “electronic nose”). This device is composed by an array of six different general-purpose gas sensors coupled to a data collection and elaboration system. Gas sensors are based on metal-oxide semiconductors, whose electrical resistance changes when exposed to an odorous gas. The electrical resistances of the sensors are then analyzed by the instrument using pattern-recognition and classification algorithms. The system has to be trained in order to couple the overall response of the sensor array to one or more odour sources. After training, the IOMS is able to identify the source of a specific odour and to give a quantification of its intensity.

EOS507E is equipped with a humidity regulation system, reference gas for automatic calibration, temperature control of the measurement chamber, gas flow control and GSM-based control module for remote control.

Figure 15: EOS507E electronic nose

2.3.5.2 Data inputs

Inputs are provided by the user directly to the instrument (touchscreen) or through remote connection.

- Operation commands

- Start/stop measurement
- Start/stop calibration
- Auto-zero
- Start/stop cleaning
- Configuration parameters
 - Measurement type (training vs monitoring, continuous vs single)
 - Sampling frequency
 - Sample flow

2.3.5.3 Data outputs

- Electrical resistance of the gas sensors
- Intensity of sensor response in instrumental units (linearization and drift correction are applied)
- Classification label (Air, odour A/B/C..., unknown) of the sampled gas
- Concentration of the sampled gas

2.3.5.4 Functionality summary

The electrical signals measured from the sensor array are converted in instrumental units (called “EOS Units”), using sensor calibration data that are generated during periodical calibration. These units are used to linearize the response of the sensors with respect to gas concentration and to correct baseline and sensitivity drifts. These features are then compared to those recorded within the training dataset using pattern recognition and classification algorithms, in order to generate the output (i.e. the measurement of the odour). The result of the measurement is shown continuously on the display (one output per second) and recorded on a storage drive inside the instrument (one output per minute).

The sensors and actuators that are responsible for flow, temperature and humidity regulation are automatically controlled by the instrument according to system configuration data. These data are automatically corrected during time in order to adapt to external variations, while the user can change them if necessary through the graphical user interface.

Finally, remote control is possible at two levels. On one side, it is possible to control the instrument from an external PC by establishing a direct connection, accessing to the same user interface that is shown on the display. On the other side, it is possible to access an external XML webservice, where the instrument sends data, while they are collected without the need for direct access to the electronic nose.

2.3.5.5 Component diagram

Figure 16: The SACMI EOS507E olfactory system diagram

2.3.6 ITK Daedalus Edge (SENSAP)

2.3.6.1 Component Description

The Integra Traceability Kit (ITK) Daedalus Edge device is part of Sensap Swiss AG Integra product line. Through its modular design, Daedalus besides its core functionality of data acquisition and signal processing, it has a variety of modules related to machinery production, as in-Line vision inspection modules for product quality and defect detection and “smart” Tag module for traceability and automate machine recipe loading.

Daedalus integrates with the most popular EIS systems (i.e. ERP, WMS, MRP), providing automatic and reliable synchronization of warehouse and shop-floor resources (i.e. labor, equipment, tools, and materials) with standing managerial data, while enabling real-time, remote visibility of operations performance through WEB-based customizable dashboards.

The main functionality of Daedalus within the iQonic system is to act as the IoT gateway. It will provide the communication connection from the Demo Cases Shop floors to the higher-level components of the iQonic system. Besides that, the ITK will employ a variety of its own sensors (i.e. optical, accelerometers, temperature) in any Demo case needed defined by the Use case analysis. Based on the Demo cases and of each individual use cases, several modules of the ITK Daedalus will be used and new functionalities will be developed in the frame and needs of the iQonic system.

2.3.6.2 Main ITK Daedalus Edge inputs

- Alarms, Events and Notifications from other IQONIC sub – systems
- Various Sensor Raw Data
- Data sources from iQonic devices/machine
 - SACMI – Electronic “Nose”
 - FiconTec – Photonics assembly and Testing Machine
 - FORTH - Adaptive in-process optics for quality inspection
 - Shadow – Robot Hand
- RFID tag data
- Operator Input (through HMI, Push Buttons)
- Vision Quality Inspection data (i.e. quality grade)

2.3.6.3 Main ITK Daedalus Edge outputs

- Visual Alerts/Status/Notification/Messages
 - Stack Light
 - HMI
- KPI calculations (i.e. UpTime, DownTime)
- Aggregated pre-defined data model
- RFID tag write/update data

2.3.6.4 ITK Daedalus Edge functionality summary

Key Features:

- Measurement Extraction
 - Sensors installed to the machinery
 - values continuously updated
 - Machinery inter-Connection
 - Extract measures from Signals
- KPI Calculation Process
 - Calculate KPIs such as OEE, Downtime, Up time, Idle time
- Visualization module
 - Visualize measures, KPIs and Events/Alarms/Notifications
- Gets input from barcode scanner (vision, optical)/RFID tags
- Send measures
 - Send aggregated data to iLike platform (Holonix)
- Vision Inspection
 - Defect detection (Optional)
- “smart” Tag
 - Reading/Writing RFID tag with data related to product state

2.3.6.5 Component diagram

Figure 17: ITK Daedalus Edge diagram

2.3.7 Higher Level Communication Middleware – HLCM (ATLANTIS)

2.3.7.1 Component Description

Higher Level Communication Middleware (HLCM) will be industry standardized (IEC 62714, IEC 62264, OPC-UA) communication interface among Manufacturing Execution System (MES) / Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and other higher level management components i.e., Reverse Supply Chain (RSC) and Decision Support System (DSS), as well as the Machine Level Communication Middleware (i-Like Machines), where RESTful Web APIs will be implemented with ASP.NET Core 3, for interfacing with the components. The HLCM will aim to provide solutions to frequently encountered problems, such as heterogeneity, interoperability, security and dependability. First, heterogeneity of different objects will be addressed as the HLCM sits between MES / ERP and other applications, operating a reliable communication among involved s/w components with different interfaces, operating systems and their architectures. Secondly, interoperability is a vital functionality for HLCM, that will make it possible for two sets of interconnected networks to be able to meaningfully exchange data and services, with different assumptions on protocols, data models and configuration. HLCM will be designed according to the standardized protocols and communication means i.e., OPC, OPC-UA, UMCM. Furthermore, security will be achieved by ensuring authentication of identification and credentials, authorized modifications and access control policy. Additionally, HLCM system will expose maintainability by responding to failures properly and by rapidly returning them to normal functionality without any problem. Finally, resource discovery mechanism for HLCM should cope with frequent failures. Therefore, self-stabilizing algorithms are to be used to bring the system into an ordinary state despite transient failures.

2.3.7.2 Main HLCM inputs and outputs

The main possible HLCM data inputs are coming from various data sources. Below a list of these possible inputs is given:

- Processed and/or simulated sensorial data from the Machine Level Communication Middleware (i-Like Machines).
- Data from MES / ERP Systems
 - Tracked KPIs
 - Production orders (ID, Issue date)
 - Production orders detail (product, total_quantity)
 - Production execution (start date/time, stop date/time, quantity)
 - Product
 - Technical characteristics (characteristic, value)
 - Normal value ranges of the technical characteristics
 - Physical units

2.3.7.3 HLCM functionality summary

MQTT technology as Message Broker will be used for HLCM, that will use publish / subscribe communication pattern. An information supplier publishes messages that are forwarded to one or more subscribers (one-to-many communication), while an extension to this basic model allows messages being associated to topics. The subscribers only receive messages associated with the exact topic(s) to which they have subscribed. The key elements in the publish / subscribe communication are the notification service and the buffer, where the messages are queued before they are passed to subscribers. The notification service takes responsibility to inform the subscribers when a new message arrives. In this way, HLCM allows the asynchronous communication between producers and consumers as a fully decoupled. This loose coupling is the prime advantage of this kind of communication in the context of ad-hoc environments. HLCM as an extra layer is applied to the communication with other higher-level management systems i.e. DSS, RSC, as well as Machine Level Communication Middleware (i-Like Machines).

2.3.7.4 Component diagram

Figure 18: HLCM diagram

2.3.8 Knowledge based system KBS (HOLONIX)

2.3.8.1 Component description and functionality

The Knowledge Based System has been developed as component of iLike Machines (ILM) platform, proposed by HOLONIX, aiming at providing an advanced management of huge quantities of data in the field of machinery management. The systems provides a robust layer for long term sensor data storage, whose typical use case scenarios are related to the access to data for verifications (e.g. in case of tracking down some issue) and to the retrieval of data in batches (e.g. for training the reasoning components and, when required, feeding the high level components of iQonic). IML and its elements (including KBS) are positioned in iQonic architecture according to logical schema depicted in Figure 19.

The KBS includes three main key features, respectively related to data storage, data ingestion and data retrieval.

1. The technology selected for recording the sensor data is Apache Cassandra, a free and open-source, distributed, wide column store, NoSQL database management system. Cassandra is designed to handle large amounts of data across many commodity servers, providing high availability with no single point of failure. Cassandra can be well suited for retrieving time series data, as this use case requires, and provides the full feature set even with the community edition, while other competitors (e.g. Influx DB) allow certain features only in paid versions. Clustering features provided by the KBS are used and prove useful in case of a larger scale deployment.
2. A component for data ingestion store gets the sensor data (whose format is compliant with predefined schemas and formats) from a topic of the Machine level communication middleware, merges them with the other domain / context information present into a service of registry and then writes the enriched data into the db.
3. A layer of data retrieval consisting of web services and endpoints. In particular, access to the data has been wrapped with a HTTP API exposed by this element of the KBS. In this way, no need to learn and

deal with the technicalities of the Cassandra drivers is required by the other partners, since they can use HTTP requests, that are already widespread in other components of the iQonic platform. Streaming techniques have been implemented to access the data stored in an efficient way, avoiding abnormal resource consumption with the expected high amount of data.

Figure 19: iLike Machines and KBS positioning inside iQonic architecture

2.3.8.2 Main KBS inputs and outputs

The main possible KBS data inputs are coming from various data sources (sensors, ITK Daedalus Edge, etc.) through the Machine Level Communication Middleware, after possible pre-processing. Below a list of these possible inputs is given:

- Various Sensor Raw Data
- RFID tag data
- Operator Input (through HMI, Push Buttons)
- Vision Quality Inspection data (i.e. quality grade)

2.3.9 New iLike Machine Platform functionalities (HOLONIX)

2.3.9.1 Component description and functionalities

iLike Machines component represents one of the main interoperability elements in iQonic platform, providing a messaging layer enabling the communication both with the field and among the other upper modules of iQonic, according to the functional schema of the Figure 19. It is composed of two main elements: Machine Level Communication Middleware and Rabbit MQ. Machine Level Communication Middleware represents a “Field to Cloud” layer of the IoT stack, allowing data collected from the “field” (e.g. sensors devices, ITK Daedalus, etc.) to be carried to the cloud infrastructure (i.e. the KBS), where they can be stored, enriched and processed. RabbitMQ is a messaging system based on AMQP, enabling a publishing / subscribing mechanism and checking how messages are structured and written. Messages can arrive from:

- An internal virtual gateway, which is an internal application that receives the messages from the devices, after a step of validation (compliance with AVRO schema) and interpretation.
- Other services, i.e. the upper modules of iQonic

New functionalities leverage the following main concepts:

- **Multitenancy.** For resources optimization, iLike Machines can operate in multitenant mode. In respect of the field to cloud communication, a tenant defines an isolated environment dedicated to a customer or a project. iLike Machines does not provide a built-in method to transfer data from one tenant to another.
- **Type of communication.** The communication from the field to the cloud platform can happen following two schemas: direct mode, when a device sends data about itself, and delegated mode, when an intermediary (gateway) sends data about (one or) more devices
- **Device types.** Device types are a logical grouping of devices that share common traits, typically they map to types of equipment. Devices are hereby instances of a given device type.
- **Data series and schemas.** A device type contains also the definitions of the message types that will be exchanged in form of data series. They have a unique name within the device type, a schema that describes the structure of the data exchanged and a set of parameters that control how the data will be treated. Typically, data series map to the collection of parameters, that share functional meaning, data types and sampling time. Enforcement of a schema is a focal point of communication. It ensures that no unexpected data is processed within the platform and establishes a contract between the parties implementing the field and the cloud sides of the communication. Data series schemas are defined following the Apache Avro specification (<https://avro.apache.org/>)
- **MQTT communication channel.** For the communication from field to cloud the MQTT protocol (version 3.1.1 - <http://mqtt.org/>) is used, as it is a widely supported protocol, well suited for sending telemetry data with low overhead and a small implementation footprint. In normal operation, the communication MUST happen by using TLS encryption (also referred sometimes as SSL, available typically on port 8883) and the access to the MQTT broker is granted by providing valid credentials.

2.3.9.2 Main iLike Machines inputs and outputs

The main possible iLike Machines data inputs are coming from various data sources (sensors, ITK Daedalus Edge, etc.) and from other IQONIC sub - systems (DSS, RSC, etc.)

- Alarms, Events and Notifications
- Various Sensor Raw Data
- RFID tag data
- Operator Input (through HMI, Push Buttons)
- Vision Quality Inspection data (i.e. quality grade)

2.3.10 Early Malfunction Detection and Prediction Inference Engine (CORE)

2.3.10.1 Component Description

This software component will be delivered as an arrangement of cloud deployed agents offering the different functionalities. One of functionalities will be to detect the state of the machine and the deviation from the “norm” with respect to product quality. The other functionality will be to predict the state of the machine within a certain time horizon with respect to product quality again. Both agents will ingest streaming data from the shopfloor (from Sensap and Holonix) and perform their activities in real time in discrete intervals. This is an intermediate component that produces outputs, which are utilized by other components downstream (such as the DSS by Atlantis).

2.3.10.2 CORE ML Main inputs

A list of possible sources is given:

- Streaming sensor data
- Machine settings
- Product quality characteristics from upstream processes
- Process KPIs
- Process Start/Stop times
- Process processing speed

- Production numbers

2.3.10.3 CORE ML Main outputs

The main outputs of the agents:

- Detect Abnormal Machine Behavior
- Estimate machine production quality degradation

2.3.10.4 CORE ML Functionality summary

Although there are 2 main agents providing functionalities, there are a lot of support systems to enable these.

- Streaming databases to store data needed for inference inputs
- Connectors to ingest data from sources
- Connectors to push data or receive get requests from consumers
- Microservice agents to pre-process data
- Microservice agents to push data to ML agents
- ML agents to provide inference

2.3.10.5 Component diagram

Figure 20: CORE ML diagram

2.3.11 Reverse Supply Chain (RSC) Process Strategy (ATLANTIS)

2.3.11.1 Component Description

Reverse Supply Chain (RSC) process strategy refers to the movement of material/parts/products from consumer to supplier, following the reverse logic of the traditional supply chain (movement of goods from supplier to consumer), that consumes information of defected products/parts, in order to decide their possible redirection, either to upstream stages (internal or external supply-chain tiers) for remanufacturing, or to other supply-chain tiers for possible disassembly, recycling or disposal, depending on the recoverability and the recovery cost of the part. A rule-based engine will be used, with rules defining the conditions to be met (e.g. defect severity and type, recoverable, value to recover, reparable, defect origin, stage, internal/external supply tier, etc.). The rules will also take into consideration the involved stages and tiers, and conditions for product/part reuse and requalification, as well as the process chain characteristics realized in each project use case. Furthermore, the collaboration with Cyber Physical System (CPS) will be established, where its knowledge-based system and the data gathered in-line, will be used by RSC for visualizing the best defect management option. RSC will define the semantic rules for the reverse process based on use-case input analysis.

2.3.11.2 Main Reverse Supply Chain inputs

The main RSC data inputs are coming from the following sources:

- Live CPS sensorial data
- Historical sensorial data from other defective cases

Context aware algorithms need the following input:

- The current production stage.
- The current tier (internal, external).
- The corresponding supplier.
- The part's type of defect.
- The severity of the defect.
- The criteria to decide the next step / action to suggest (i.e. rule-based decision support).

2.3.11.3 Main Reverse Supply Chain outputs

The main RSC outputs in the iQonic system are listed below:

- Suggested action (Recycle, repair, return to supplier).
- Classification context (internal or external tier).
- Data to repository.
- HMI (Human-Machine Interface).

2.3.11.4 Reverse Supply Chain functionality summary

iQonic will apply the RCS concept and policies, by considering a multistage production, differentiating between internal and external tiers, making use of tracking sensorial/historical data that the CPS could provide to RSC for further analysis.

- Internal tiers are the Stages (Stage i , $i=1\dots n$) of the multistage production.
- External tiers are 3rd party suppliers of materials or product parts, or other internal production lines of the factory.

The iQonic RSC strategy has the following steps:

1. When a defected part is detected at the Stage i , a reverse flow process will be triggered, so that the part goes at least one stage back in the supply chain.
2. Context aware algorithms will identify the part and classify it as product of an internal (i.e. upstream Stage $i-1$) or external tier.
3. If the part comes from an internal tier, a selection and sorting process will be activated, following the evaluation of whether or not the part has any value to justify its retrieval cost:
 - a. If there is enough recoverable value, it is redirected for repair/rework in upstream stages;
 - b. If not, it is redirected for recycling.
4. If the part comes from an external tier, it will be redirected to the supplier or for proper disposal/recycling.

The overview of the functions concerning the user interface will be:

- Statistics: Displays the general statistical overview of the software's present state.
- Product types: Displays the product types.
- Defect Types: Displays the defect types.
- Defect Causes: Displays the defect causes, including a short description.
- Defects: Displays all defects in a table, including the product type, the defection cause, etc.
- Rules: Thoroughly displays the existing rules and enables the user to create new ones.
- Suggestions: Displays all system suggestions that are presently available, enabling the user to either accept or decline them.
- Actions: Displays all existing/possible system actions.
- Measurement Units: Simply displays the measurement units (SI) used in rules.

2.3.11.5 Component diagram

Figure 21: RSC diagram

2.3.12 CPS for defects evaluation for reuse-requalification of products (POLIMI)

Defect management policies, commonly adopted in manufacturing systems, are scrapping and off-line reworking of defective items. The application of these expensive and low added-value alternatives is mainly due to the late identification of the defect in multi-stage systems, typically based on end-of-line inspection. As a consequence, scrapping and reworking result into significant economic losses, because of the value of scrapped parts or the production time wasted for reworking, thus undermining the achievement of target due-date performance of the line, ultimately resulting in a loss of competitiveness for the manufacturer. On the contrary, when in-line monitoring and inspection is adopted, especially for high-value parts, defects can be detected in line and requalification or reuse practices can potentially be activated with lower complexity and higher efficiency.

However, this requires the development of innovative in-line Cyber-Physical-Systems (CPSs), able to quickly elaborate sensor data by advanced algorithms, to adjust the process and correct the defect or, if not possible, reuse valuable components through disassembly and regeneration operations. CPSs are usually defined as systems integrating computation and physical actuation capabilities, thus enabling model-based, feed-forward control of complex multi-stage process chains. IQONIC will thus develop a new methodology, software tool and hardware implementation of a system for avoiding the propagation of defects in multi-stage optoelectronics process chains, by adapting the downstream process settings depending on the quality characteristics of the components processed at upstream stages, observed by in-line inspection (Figure Y). These innovative approaches could bring huge gains in quality, productivity and sustainability performance, mainly by reducing the generation of waste, reducing reworking efforts and increasing the robustness of the system in meeting its target due-dates. These new results have clearly indicated the advantage of proactive defect mitigation solutions against traditional reactive solutions.

Figure 22: Machine and system level actuation and control implemented by CPSs

The architecture of this system is briefly explained in the following, together with its core components and building blocks. From a control system perspective, the simplified block diagram of a feed-forward controller is shown in Figure X.

Figure 23: Simplified block diagram of CPSs

The output of a given production process is controlled towards the target performance by using a feed-forward approach. According to measured output components from one of more upstream production processes, the parameters of the downstream controlled production process are adjusted by a model-based approach, in order to smooth variability and avoid an input defect to be translated into an output non-conforming part. This is done through two main transfer functions, acting both on the flow control level ($C_p(z)$) and on the process parameters ($C_f(z)$).

In terms of key building blocks and components, the following Figure P explains the interacting modules that are composing a CPS for controlling production process M_j , based on the measured output of the production process M_i .

Figure 24: Architecture and software modules of a CPSs

The gathered signals and data obtained by inspection devices adopted to observe the output of process M_i are further elaborated by a set of software modules:

- A *process meta-model*, usually physics-based, which elaborates the data gathered at stage M_i and makes use of nominal product data, to predict the output quality performance characteristics of the component, that will be processed at stage M_j , under a given set of process parameters and flow logistics settings.
- An *optimization model*, which iterates with the process meta-model to trigger changes to the process parameters and flow logistics, for example routing or dispatching rules, adopted at stage M_j to force towards the target output quality characteristics the outcome of process M_j , thus correcting possible variabilities originated at the upstream stage M_i .
- A control module, which visualizes the optimal settings to be assigned to the controlled process at M_j to the user, i.e. the operator, waiting for a validation, assessment and transferring of the adjusted settings to the controlled process M_j .

Therefore, the CPSs will consider the human-in-the-loop paradigm, as a stating implementation and won't be fully automatic, in order to ensure traceability, reporting and operators learning, very important assets in real industrial settings. The development of this CPS framework within WP5 will be tested and validated within specific use-cases in all the IQONIC demo-cases.

2.3.13 Defect Severity DSS (ATLANTIS)

2.3.13.1 Component Description

Defect Severity DSS software provides an analytical synopsis of severity of defect and the recyclability/reusability score the production material in the IQONIC manufacturing system. Its main functionality is to acquire the necessary information from the manufacturing and assembly process, diagnose the causal relations of defect generation, and effectively provide a prognosis of the state of the system. The prognosis will lead to improved optimisation of the process chain operations and defect management, based on strategies for improving defect life – cycle management, user recommendations including risk mitigating actions on identified defects. Recommendations based on the IQONIC strategies will be provided by the DSS. The IQONIC strategies exploit optimisation factors such as data uncertainty, lack of information and information quality, involvement of multiple actors, events and alarms from the diagnostic quality inspection and monitoring layers. DSS also includes semantic rules, which define the defective parts and the methods for the mitigating actions. A KPI mechanism within the DSS is able to rank the severity detections and the recommendations based on a well – established protocol. The mechanism also measures the DSS suggestions and their relevance in order to train the system for better future responses. Continuously incoming data is used to train the system's algorithms and improve its performance. A database is used for storing the recommendations feedback, which allows data storage and retrieval for training purposes. The DSS database also includes the implemented strategies outputs and exploits them in the machine learning processes of the system.

2.3.13.2 Main Defect Severity DSS inputs

The main DSS data inputs are coming from various data sources. Below a list of the possible inputs is given:

- Live sensorial data
- Historical data from various external systems
- Alarms from other IQONIC sub – systems
- Predictions for the defect detection and severity
- Predictions from data analysis sub – components
- KRIs which compute the risk mitigation actions
- Recommendations feedback
- KRIs feedback

2.3.13.3 Main Defect Severity DSS outputs

The main DSS outputs in the IQONIC system are listed below:

- Recommendations for defect detection and severity
- Maintenance recommendation based on the predictions or live/historical data

- KPI recommendations for improved functionality
- Notifications based on the alarms
- Reports based on the KPIs, in the forms of data charts, graphs etc
- Strategies outputs and actions
- Strategies suggestions and exploitable recommendations

2.3.13.4 Defect Severity DSS functionality summary

The DSS has several sub – components which work seamlessly to create the recommendations and suggestions of a decision support system. The main functionalities of the system are:

- Optimisation process of defect severity
The system creates suggestion and recommendations based on strategies, incoming data and predictions and exploits it for better recommendations
- Semantic rules component
 - **Rule engine:** a system – subcomponent which runs the user defined rules. Supports rules, priority, functions and combinations. It provides users the functionality to apply their own rules based on processes and the system relates the rules with the ontology entities of the IQONIC system
- KPI mechanism
The sub – component which computes KPIs for defect detection, strategies actions and measures their effectiveness with a well – established KPI protocol. The output indicates the performance and the improvement of the suggestions and recommendations of the DSS
- HMI
Allows the interaction between the system and the user
 - **UI:** allows the user to define the rules in the rule engine along with the parameters, conditions etc
 - **Visualisation:** creates the reports with graphs and charts for the KPI mechanism
- Data persistence
Creates the database schema and implores the all the necessary database actions:
 - **Data storage** (input data)
 - **Output storage** (output data)
 - **Intermediate storage** (rules, suggestions, actions, parameters, triggers, failure modes etc.)

2.3.13.5 Component diagram

Figure 25: DSS diagram

2.3.14 Predictive maintenance system (FICONTEC)

Within the iQonic project two commercially available bonding and assembly machines will be used for the two specific use cases of Prima Electro, as well as for Alpes Laser. Both machines are based on standard machines, which are slightly modified within the project, to fulfil the higher requirements for data logging.

In the case of Prima Electro a AL500-AA machine will be used, which is specially developed for the assembly of laser pump modules. All ficonTEC machines are already equipped with a large amount of sensors like e.g. temperature, vacuum, pressure, motor current and axes positions, which can provide a constant flow of data during the assembly process. However, within a normal assembly process only a small fraction of this sensor data is logged to ensure a proper process flow. Within the iQonic project the assembly process of this machine will be modified in a way that much more data from the already implemented data sources is collected. This data is streamed via a specially developed channel and thereby made available for the ITK and HLCM system. In addition to this already existing sensors, the machine will be also equipped with additional data sources like acceleration sensors, additional temperature sensors and humidity sensors.

Figure 26: ficonTEC assembly machine AL500-AA (left) and close-up of an assembly process similar to the one for the Prima Electro use case

In the application case of Alpes Laser a BL500 machine will be used within the project. This machine is developed for laser to submount assemblies and consists of an high-accuracy alignment engine, a separate alignment engine for ensuring a parallelism of the laser and the submount, as well as of an oven for the soldering process. As all the standard machine, also this machine is equipped with lots of sensors, which will be used for data acquisition within the project. Similar, as in the case of the AL500-AA machine, also this machine will be equipped with additional sensor for data acquisition, which finally are streamed to the ITK and HLCM systems.

During the assembly process different kind of data will be made available for the HLCM. On the one hand this will be sensor data like vacuum or pressurized air levels at different positions of the machine, which can give some indications for abnormalities. The values of temperature sensors installed in several crucial points of the machine, like in the working area (to detect temperature changes close to the components), on the moving parts of the alignment system (to detect temperature changes introduced by the axes) or in the general interior or also outside of the machine (to detect temperature variations due to changing environmental conditions). Besides, this easy accessible sensor data, which most likely changes only on the 100ms time scale, also motor currents, positions feedback, position errors, settling times for axes and many more will be supervised. As these values may change on a shorter time scale in the ms range, a higher measurement frequency is required to prevent missing some important events.

The results coming back from the DSS towards the assembly machines are a sophisticated analysis of the machine status and performance. This data potentially reveals connections between different machine sensor value and final machine performance which will not be detectable otherwise.

The information from the the DSS system will not only provide a clear analysis of the machine status, but also will allow for interventions for the predictive maintenance measures. In this way, not only the yield of the assembly, but also the machine uptime can be significantly increased.

2.3.14.1 Functionality summary

The assembly machine devoted to this project, will be adapted to deliver lots of sensor information e.g. from axes performance, positioning errors, intensity of the alignment signal, pressure and vacuum values and more. In addition, the assembly machine will be equipped with additional sensors, providing a plus of useful data, compared to standard assembly machines, about acceleration of axes, humidity and temperature at different locations in the machine. This data will be provided to the ITK and HLCM and combined with more sensor values. As a feedback the machine receives information of the recent machine status and the DSS may suggest actions preventing the machine from failures or actions aiming on increasing the yield.

3 Use Case Application Draft

The iQonic solution will be employed in several demonstrators in diverse use cases. Although not all the components of the iQonic solution will be utilized in each use case, an overall evaluation of the platform will be achieved.

ALPES [21] is a semiconductor laser production company. Due to the highly customizable nature of the lasers offered by ALPES, and due to their specialty nature, the production of lasers is performed in typical batch sizes in the order of a few wafers (2-6), where each wafer contains circa 1.500 laser chips. The epitaxial growth [22] changes depending on the kind of laser, and the required parameters. Through iQonic, ALPES aims to integrate the quality control of its outsourced processes, as well as its in-house processes, into a “single window platform”, which will allow to have a better overview of the production process. In addition, ALPES aims to test in its facility the ultra-precise handling, for precise alignment of the laser chips on the submounts, as well as for automated wire bonding of the chips to the submounts. This is a highly desirable process, and is currently performed manually, with acceptable results, which could be greatly improved. Wire bonding failure is not uncommon, especially in demanding operating environments (e.g. in infrared countermeasure laser onboard fighter jet planes), and a standardized and automated process would improve the overall production yield in producing HHL packaged QCLs, which is currently in the order of 80%. Through iQonic, ALPES aims to address the quality control of the produced wafers, and also increase the quality of the sub-mounting process of the laser chips), which is now performed manually. Thus, iQonic will demonstrate that ALPES will move from:

As it is now:

High vertical production chain

- High investments and operative costs
- Difficulties in monitoring, data tracking and information ex-change
- High costs for failures
- Low production yield

As will be next:

Streamlined process driven by platform

- Increased quality control capabilities and faster testing
- Fast set up, self-calibration, and high saturation capability
- Low machine downtime
- Production and quality control integrated management platform
- Higher production yield due to automated tasks and more consistent production

The PRIMA [23] demo case will be linked to the demonstration of a lighthouse production process for the multi-stage zero defect manufacturing of Laser sources with increased quality. Through iQonic, PRIMA is planning to achieve optimized configurations of the diodes, that will make it possible to overcome customization limits, exploiting in an efficient way the laser process for different applications, according to the features of the beam. Process monitoring and information tracking, handling complex designs that include parts functionalities, optimizing product configuration and controlling performances through simulation tools, are the main technologies challenges that can be faced with iQonic, for a new, flexible, and innovative process chain. iQonic will enable an increase in the level of flexibility and modularity of the manufacturing process, tailoring the source for the specific customers' application. Flexibility will be pursued with a line created to comply with different requirements according to the features of the product, the customer, and the application. This means that the production line will be able to manufacture diodes with different power, wavelength, and geometries, reducing the time to market of new products. The infrastructure will be conceived to fully exploit the Industry 4.0 paradigm, with the use of CPS, and data analytics, it will enable to achieve a line that is reconfigurable in a short time, to customize the production. Thus, iQonic will demonstrate that PRIMA Electro will move from:

As it is now:

High vertical production chain

- Customization and flexibility not easy
- High investments and operative costs
- Difficulties in monitoring, data tracking and information exchange
- High costs for failures

As will be next:

Reconfigurable process driven by platform

- High re-configurability degree of the factory
- Fast set up, self-calibration, and high saturation capability
- Low machine downtime
- New business model based on data management, self-learning system and data storage

Filar-Optomaterials (FILAR) [24] demo case involves the manufacturing of synthetic crystals (laser, optical and scintillation) in an industrial chain starting from raw material sintering until the supply of the final product

to end user. Their main products are Crystal ingots, rods, slabs, discs and pixels. Through iQonic, FILAR expects to benefit by adding value to both on-line and off-line monitoring of the process chains, by seeking more accurate feedback to deeper understanding and analysis. In the opto-mechanical, QC and coating jobs, up-to-date sensors and instruments will also add efficiency and gain to the work process reducing production cycle time and driving the material waste to a minimum. The main focus areas of FILAR is to improve the Material regeneration, repair and reuse. These materials can mainly be identified in two origins. The first originates from residual crystal ingots after cutting and drilling. This material is partially reusable and thus stocked for the fabrication of smaller-size components or, in some cases, for the production of gem stones. The second group of materials comes in the form of used laser crystals that experience performance drop in the system and therefore need to be tested for a possible reconditioning. This regeneration is achieved through surface lapping and polishing and fresh coating. The quality control concerns almost all the properties of these crystals: conditions of the bulk material, dimensions and geometries, type and class of coating, etc. Therefore, the assessment determines the possibility of recovery usually with positive results in over than 90% of the cases. The material that is successfully recovered is almost identical to the new material and thus will be fully integrated into the production cycle, where the same control and treatment apply. iQonic will demonstrate that FILAR will move from:

- Long adjustment times to faster by 10 times while having higher quality
- Low flexibility/re-configurability due to absence of feedback to increase adaptability with real time feedback
- Low understanding of the defects generation to increased capacity to prevent defects from happening

The fabrication of BRIGHTERWAVE's [25] laser modules requires state-of-the-art optoelectronic assembly methods in terms of accuracy, speed and repeatability. The main focus of its products relies on two proprietary and revolutionary technology platforms, (i) frequency converted semiconductor laser technology for visible wavelengths and (ii) retina scanning display technology. The demonstration involves high volume production, since the target of BRIGHTERWAVE is to provide its laser-based products to millions of end-users (consumers) even on a monthly-basis. Through iQonic, BRIGHTERWAVE aims to address the increased yield through the quality control of the produced lasers, and also speed-up the reconfiguration of the processes to host the high-volume production. Besides, BRIGHTERWAVE expects to get benefited through the accurate, flexible and smart handling tool for the assembly processes done in-house. iQonic will enable an increase in yield through its inference engine and the modelling of the whole process chains. The IoT framework and the smart handling system will ensure accurate and precise placement of different components and all the sensors and actuators will be fine-tuned on-the-fly for each batch, enabling fast reconfiguration while maintaining increased quality. The CPS and DSS modules will support BRIGHTERWAVE to reduce its material costs, since any defected piece will be examined and either will go upstream (to its supplier-outsource company) for rework or will be examined to see its defect level for downstream, minimizing loss of resources, i.e. maximizing the profit. Consumer goods require the best increased customer satisfaction, which will be ensured in the design phase, through the event modelling of the overall performance indicators, allowing to configure the processes based on the sought targets (e.g. reduce costs) helping to reduce the costs. In summary, iQonic will demonstrate that BRIGHTERWAVE will move from:

- Late defect detection with increased costs to early defect detection reducing the production cost by 10%
- Low yields due to not-fully automated/calibrated processes to 20% yield increased through real-time feedback
- Long waiting and long production times to highly automated and modelled process with 16% faster production

4 Conclusions

The report provides an overview of the combined hardware and software architecture to be implemented in iQonic, as the platform to pave the way towards zero-defect manufacturing. There is a multitude of data to be generated during component manufacturing and system assembly. All of the data gathered by various sensing and measurement technologies, provided via a middleware architecture in a unified format to processing intelligence, is used to influence, adapt and control the “standard” assembly algorithms.

Main data to be generated and analysed are images that reveal information about component states and performances, as well as environmental parameters for the assembly processes and individual assembly parameters, such as positions, forces, contaminations etc...

The control to be applied are mainly the selection of individual components out of a batch, with respect to the desired and tolerable performance of the overall photonic system, and the modified position of the component during alignment, taking into account pre-compensation of assembly process effects, as well as individual performance properties of the component to be assembled.

Additional features, like the re-qualification of disassembled components for re-use, can also be implemented on the discussed architecture. The performance has to be experimentally investigated, using specific demonstrator cases.

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